

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL SKILLS IN SHAPING THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF FIRST GRADE LEARNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 1

Pages: 64-73

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2645

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14186926

Manuscript Accepted: 10-14-2024

The Role of Social Skills in Shaping the Academic Performance of First Grade Learners

Rostie C. Napone, * Emmanuel Alex Bercero
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study attempted to determine the influence of social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills to pupils' school performance. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were the mean and standard deviation to determine the extent of pupils' social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills and frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the level of pupils' school performance. Pearson r was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of pupils' school performance and the extent of pupils' social skills. Findings revealed that pupils' social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills were very highly developed and 52% of the pupils obtained a very satisfactory performance while only 4% achieved a fairly satisfactory school performance. Results imply that social skills denote negligible correlation to pupils' school performance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Subsequently, it was recommended that in order to intensify pupils' school performance, teachers need to develop engaging and authentic learning materials which develop school performance.

Keywords: *social skills, interpersonal skills, interactive skills, personal skills, school performance*

Introduction

Learning the basic human skills to effectively interact and communicate with others in the social setting through verbal and non-verbal communication such as speech, gestures, facial expression and body language requires teachers to provide the necessary environment where learning is engaging and fun.

This study is anchored on the legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to D.O. 21, series of 2019 on the policy guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program which highlights the development of social skills and enhances cognitive ability as it improves creativity and symbolic thinking of school children.

Social skills are important because they can help pupils to communicate more effectively and efficiently and, as a result, help them build, maintain and grow relationships with fellow learners, peers in school, and new contacts. These skills are important to maintain and improve social interaction to achieve understanding and collaboration.

Subsequently, the development of social skills is in consonance with the plight of the 21st century learners where each pupil will develop the mastery or needed competencies in interpersonal, communication, and social skills in order for them to successfully interact in the social environment.

Fabria and Romero (2021) asserted that the pupils' social skills are the competencies needed to achieve social development as social being, they should be familiar with the norms, rules, and values of the society in which they live and in the classroom they learn as well as to master the skills necessary for them to achieve effective social interaction within the school and classroom environment.

Additionally, it was pointed out that pupils are anticipated to work competently with numerous challenges in school and in disengaging social interaction difficulties through apposite resolutions which require their social skills. With this, teachers, apart from the K-12 curriculum, are encouraged to develop pupils' ability to socially interact and communicate with others.

It was based on the above-stated circumstance, that Katz and McClellan (2021) suggest that teachers impose to help develop pupils' social skills in order to work with other learners more effectively, develop flexibility and understanding with others, adjust to different personalities and behaviors of learners, develop emotional suppleness, and personal social-interactive skills to achieve learning competence.

Further, Zahid and Hassan (2020) asserted that pupils' social skills are critical to individual pupil's learning competence and academic success. It is closely related to interpersonal and communication skills because dealing with other learners in the classroom will help them understand and share resources needed for learning.

Social Skills are part of pupils' behavior that facilitates an understanding and adaptation across a variety of social settings. This is also considered as the basic element for the relationship formation and building or the quality of social interactions of the individuals in school environment. Gresham and Elliot (2020) asserted that schools are social places where pupils learn their social and interactional skills. The utilization of pupils' interaction skills facilitates the learning process; it is pointed out that the social-emotional learning is a necessary to optimize pupils' learning competence and success in their social interactions.

Furthermore, pupils' social skills are critical to successful functioning in school. Pupils will know what to say, how to attain good choices, and how to behave appropriately in different classroom situations. Del Prette (2021) pointed out that pupils who possess those

needed social skills can influence their academic performance, behavior, social and family relationships, and at the same time their involvement non-academic activities.

Consequently, teachers recognize the need to emphasize the development of pupils' social skills because these are essential to learning success. In fact, social skills are closely associated with human relations skills as it deals with interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, and interactive skills. Social skills are considered as human-interactive skills, societal and public skills, interpersonal skills, personal characteristics, attributes, and personality to admirably adapt according to the needs and desires of others.

Inversely, classroom activities focused mainly on the mastery of basic competencies through academic and theoretical as well as speculative learning setting aside the development of pupils' interpersonal and social skills. It is based on the earlier-stated context that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to establish the effect of development of social skills to pupils' school performance.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the influence of social skills in the development of pupils' school performance in Pagalungan Elementary Schools in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of social skills among first grade learners in Pagalungan Elementary Schools in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro in terms of:
 - 1.1. interpersonal skills;
 - 1.2. interactive; and,
 - 1.3. personal skills?
2. What is the level of pupils' academic performance when categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory;
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of social skills and level of school performance among first grade learners in Pagalungan Elementary School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adopted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the Grade 1 pupils of Pagalungan Elementary School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. There were fifty-six (56) pupil-respondents of the study who were observed and rated on their social skills while they are actively interacting with other students in the learning environment. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adapted from Fabria and Romero (2021) who conducted a study on pupils' social skills and its effect on pupils' interpersonal relations in school and academic performance.

The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is on the social skills of the pupils with sixty (60) indicators categorized under three major components; namely; interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills while the second part is on pupils' school performance which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission was asked by the researcher to the parents of Grade 1 pupils to allow their child to participate in the conduct of the study and utilize their learning competence based on their grades in the study. However, the parents were assured that the data gathered from the survey questionnaire be treated to its highest confidentiality.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulate, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of social skills of the First Grade learners.

Problem 2. Frequency counts and percentages were used to present the level of pupils' school performance.

Problem 3. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the extent of social skills and the level of pupils' school performance.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on the influence of social skills in the development of school performance among first grade pupils. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem 1. What is the extent of social skills among first grade learners in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills?

Social skills are important for human beings especially for the kids because throughout it helps them understand others and to be understood in order to maintain the rapport and relationship in school. Social skills also help pupils express their positive and negative feelings in interpersonal situations.

Researchers found out that social skills are imperative which help develop pupils in practicing active listening, paying attention to body language, showing empathy, being mindful of tone and language, practicing assertiveness, and developing emotional intelligence.

A social skills of learner is their competence in interacting and communicating with their fellow learners where social rules and relations are created, ideas are communicated, and exchanges in verbal and non-verbal communications are observed or practiced. This means that learners developed their socialization skills.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Social Skills in terms of Interpersonal Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Interpersonal skill is taught to enhance pupils' social awareness	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
2. Interpersonal skill is taught to enhance pupils' ability to work with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
3. Interpersonal skill is taught to cope with others' peace.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
4. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' social intelligence.	4.82	.386	Very Highly Developed
5. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to collaborate with others in learning.	4.82	.386	Very Highly Developed
6. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' awareness of the social world.	4.82	.386	Very Highly Developed
7. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' social influence.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
8. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop teamwork and collaboration.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
9. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to recognize that others are important.	4.83	.370	Very Highly Developed
10. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to treat others fairly.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
11. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to relate well with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
12. Interpersonal skill is taught to enhance pupils' self-worth in social environment.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
13. Interpersonal skill is taught to cope with others in peace.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
14. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to socialize with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
15. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' motivation to learn with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
16. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to trust others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
17. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' social-interactive skills.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
18. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop cooperation and relationship with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
19. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to reciprocate to others' good deeds.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
20. Interpersonal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to respect others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
Overall Mean	4.96	.076	Very Highly Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' social skills in terms of interpersonal skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Very Highly Developed" with a mean of 4.96 ($SD=.076$). This result indicates that teachers developed the social skills among learners especially the pupils' interpersonal skills in order to effectively relate with fellow learners in the school environment. It can be deduced based on findings that teachers do not just teach but extremely developed pupils' interpersonal skills to create and maintain meaningful personal relationships with fellow learners in school. Pupils with excellent interpersonal skills can easily communicate with others in the classroom, share and build healthy relationships with their classmates and learn better with each other, developed strong support and will make learning more fun.

Lazar (2021) averred that interpersonal skills development among learners promote engagements, collaboration, and partnerships in the learning activities and performance tasks. This will also help stimulates positive contribution to group effort which facilitates completion of class tasks, develop pupils' cohesiveness and competence, and academic skills which encompasses multiple softskills among first-generational learners.

The indicators which state that "interpersonal skills were taught by teachers to develop pupils' social awareness, ability to work with others, to cope with others' peace, social influence, collaboration and teamwork, treat others fairly, relate well with others, enhance self-worth, socialize with others, motivate and trust others, interact and develop rapport with others, and respect with others" obtained the highest mean of 5.00 ($SD=.000$) which is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed". The results indicate that teachers taught interpersonal skills in order to develop pupils' ability to interact and communicate with others to help start, build, and sustain relationships.

It can be deduced based on findings that interpersonal skills are important because they often form the base of pupils' personal relationships with other learners and help them interact with others. These skills typically help pupils develop their emotional intelligence and how they communicate their need for understanding and learning. Silva (2021) asserted that interpersonal skills are crucial for pupils' communication and academic success. Their interpersonal skills help them communicate with teachers and peers and facilitate a positive learning environment, encourages collaboration, and enhances critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.82 ($SD=.386$) is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed" in the indicators "Interpersonal skills is taught to develop pupils' social intelligence, ability to collaborate with others in learning, and awareness of the social world". The results imply that teachers exceptionally developed pupils' social astuteness to relate with other learners, their aptitude to collaborate with classmates in learning activities, and develop consciousness or cognizance to shared responsibilities as learners. It can be inferred based on findings that the development of pupils' interpersonal skills help develop their ability to communicate, listen actively, work collaboratively, and handle learning concerns effectively. These are some of the key interpersonal skills that pupils need to extremely developed.

Further, it can be deduced that pupils with strong interpersonal skills can build better personal relationships with their fellow learners, teachers, and other learning participants. Acevedo (2021) affirmed that interpersonal skills as a social skill apply to the ease and efficacy with which the pupils interact with others. They rely on these skills to communicate and collaborate with others in everyday learning activities.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Social Skills in terms of Interactive Skills

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. Interactive skill is taught to enhance pupils' ability to express ideas and opinion to others	4.64	.483	Very Highly Developed
2. Interactive skill is taught to enhance pupils' ability to speak and convey information.	4.64	.483	Very Highly Developed
3. Interactive skills are taught to cope with others in peaceful communication.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
4. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to be concise in words and utterance.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
5. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to participate in conversation.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
6. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' awareness that communication is important	4.83	.371	Very Highly Developed
7. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to understand and comprehend others	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
8. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to encode information correctly.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
9. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to decode information	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
10. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to convey information effectively.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
11. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to receive feedback effectively.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
12. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to participate effectively in oral discourse	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
13. Interactive skill is taught to cope with pupils' inability to communicate	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
14. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to communicate in social setting.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
15. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to listen with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
16. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to communicate in multilingual class	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
17. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' communicative & interactive skills.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
18. Interactive skill is taught to develop understanding of non-verbal signals.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
19. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to process information.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
20. Interactive skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to use non-verbal expressions.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
Overall Mean	4.96	.067	Very Highly Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' social skills in terms of interactive skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Very Highly Developed" with a mean of 4.96 (SD=.067). This result indicates that teachers developed the social skills among learners especially the pupils' interactive skills in order to effectively interact with other learners in the classroom. It can be deduced based on findings that teachers do not just teach how pupils relate and interact with their classmates in school but they are also extremely concerned on the development of pupils to learn through social interaction such as the interactive interaction which include group discussion, question-and-answer sessions, and tutoring in order for the pupils to communicate and interact in a classroom social setting.

The indicators which state that "interactive skill is taught to cope with others in peaceful communication, develop ability to be concise in words and utterances, participate in conversation, understand and comprehend others, correctly encode and decode information, convey information effectively, receive feedback and participate in oral discourses, listen effectively, communicate in social setting, use non-verbal signals and non-verbal expressions" obtained the highest mean of 5.00 (SD=.000) which is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed". The results indicate that teachers taught interactive skills in order to develop pupils' ability to interact, communicate, and comprehend with others to help pupils effectively and efficiently relate with other learners.

It can be deduced based on findings that interactive skills are imperative because it help pupils engage in hyper-stimulated environment, interactive learning sharpens critical thinking skills, which are fundamental to the development of analytic reasoning. Martin (2021) asserted that interactive learning provides benefits to learners such as developing their cooperative and thinking as well as problem solving skills. Pupils' cooperation skills are quickly developed when pupils are motivated to work with their peers in class performance tasks and will encourage exploration of different ideas in order to strengthen their capabilities in dealing with classroom problem-solving activities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.64 (SD=.483) is verbally described as "Very Highly Developed" in the indicators "Interactive skill is taught to enhance pupils' ability to express ideas and opinion to others" and "Interactive skill is taught to enhance pupils' ability to speak and convey information". The results imply that teachers remarkably developed pupils' social perspicacity to interact with other learners, their capacity to express ideas and opinion as well as to convey information to others are important skills to succeed in their academic activities. It can be inferred based on findings that the development of pupils' interactive skills contributes their ability to effectively relate and interact with others in the classroom.

Further, it can be deduced that pupils with strong interactive skills can build strong collaborative skills and effective communication skills with their fellow learners, teachers, and other learning participants. Acevedo (2021) affirmed that interactive skills as a social skill apply to the ease and efficacy with which the pupils interact with others. They rely on these skills to communicate and collaborate with others in everyday learning activities.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Social Skills in terms of Personal Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupils' self-awareness	4.50	.504	Very Highly Developed
2. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupils' self-control	4.32	.471	Very Highly Developed
3. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' skill to cope with others.	4.83	.370	Very Highly Developed
4. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' emotional intelligence.	4.83	.370	Very Highly Developed
5. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' motivation to learning.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
6. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to understand oneself, social awareness	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
7. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' personal influence.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
8. Personal skill is taught to develop ability to collaborate in teamwork and group activities.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
9. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to relate with others	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
10. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' listening competencies.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
11. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupils' self-worth.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
12. Personal skill is taught to enhance pupils' self-regulation.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
13. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' skill to cooperate with others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
14. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' skills to understand their feelings and attitudes.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
15. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' personal attachment to learning.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
16. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' awareness of their roles in learning.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
17. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' ability to consider others.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
18. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' skills to contribute effort to achieve goals.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
19. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' conviction to take responsibility in school.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
20. Personal skill is taught to develop pupils' skills in developing camaraderie.	5.00	.000	Very Highly Developed
Overall Mean	4.92	.086	Very Highly Developed

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Developed/3.41-4.20 Highly Developed/2.61-3.40 Moderately Developed/1.81-2.60 Less Developed/1.00-1.80 Not Developed

Table 1.3 displays the mean distribution of the pupils' social skills in terms of personal skills. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Very Highly Developed" with a mean of 4.92 (SD=.086). This result indicates that teachers exceedingly developed the personal skills among learners in order to effectively understand themselves and that of other learners. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers extremely developed pupils' strong personal skills to be better equipped to communicate effectively, resolve learning issues, and work collaboratively with other learners. These skills can help pupils succeed in academic settings, as well as in

their learning performance and personal relationship with other learners.

The indicators which state that “personal skill is taught to develop pupils’ motivation to learning, ability to understand oneself and social awareness, develop personal influence, collaborate and teamwork, relate with other learners, listen with others and exercise self-regulation, cooperate and understand the feelings of others, personal attachments to learning, awareness of their roles, understand and consider others, contribute efforts, take responsibility in school activities, and skills in developing camaraderie and strong relationships” obtained the highest mean of 5.00 (SD=.000) which is verbally described as “Very Highly Developed”. The results indicate that teachers taught personal skills in order to develop pupils’ ability to understand themselves, others, and the entire school community. Additionally, they also work collaboratively with other learners.

It can be deduced based on findings that personal skills are imperious because it helps pupils personally involved in learning and in dealing with other learners. Acevedo (2021) averred that personal skills provides strong influence what pupils choose to do for learning because pupils with strong personal skills are better equipped to understand and communicate effectively, solve problems, and work collaboratively with others. These skills can help pupils succeed in academic activities, as well as in their personal relationships with other learners.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.32 (SD=.471) is verbally described as “Very Highly Developed” in the indicators “Personal skill is taught to enhance pupils’ self-control”. The result implies that teachers extremely developed pupils’ personal skills in order to enhance pupils’ self-control and regulations. It can be inferred based on findings that the development of pupils’ personal skills help contributes to pupils’ ability to effectively communicate others, develop understanding, and exercise personal restraint or self-discipline.

Further, it can be deduced that pupils with strong personal skills can build strong collaborative and effective communication skills with their fellow learners, and teachers. Martin (2021) stated that personal skills influence pupils’ efficacy in dealing with other learners. They rely on these skills to personally and effectively interact, communicate, and collaborate with others in the learning environment.

Problem 2. What is the levels of pupils’ school performance when categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectation?

Pupils’ school performance or academic performance is measured in terms of mastery of the learning proficiencies and the development of essential skills required for success in academic activities. Learning performance is categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations. Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils’ school performance.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of Students’ School Performance*

<i>Pupils’ School Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	17	30%
Very Satisfactory	29	52%
Satisfactory	8	14%
Fairly Satisfactory	2	4%
Did not meet the expectation	0	0%
Total	56	100%

As seen, 29 (52%) of the first grade pupils achieved “Very Satisfactory” in their school performance. This finding implies that there were more first grade pupils who performed remarkably adept in the learning and performed the different school and academic activities.

Thus, it is imperative for teachers to encourage pupils to develop their social skills in order to effectively learn through the provision of learner-centered and performance-based learning activities which inspire participation and engagement in school tasks and at the same time motivate pupils to learn and strengthen performance. Polinar (2021) asserted that the pupils’ school performance is predictive of the development of their interactive, interpersonal, and personal skills which are necessary in their social relationship and academic success.

On the contrary, 2 (4%) indicates that the respondents manifest a “Fairly Satisfactory” school performance. This implies that only few grade school pupils have fairly satisfactory performance. Pupils impartially performed their school and academic activities, they can work reasonably in their school and academic performance tasks. Barrera (2022) avowed that pupils who less developed their interactive, interpersonal, and personal skills cannot perform well in their school and academic activities because they cannot associate and relate well with other learners.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils’ school performance and the extent of their social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the pupils’ school performance and their social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between Pupils' School Performance and Their Social Skills*

<i>Pupils' Social Skills</i>	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig 2-tailed</i>	<i>Pupils' School Performance</i>	
			<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Interpersonal Skills	.015	.913	Denotes Negligible correlation	Accepted
Interactive Skills	.081	.551	Denotes negligible correlation	Accepted
Personal Skills	.026	.850	Denotes Negligible correlation	Accepted

*significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' school performance and their social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills. Results revealed that pupils' interpersonal skills denote "Negligible correlation" to first grade pupils' school performance ($r=.015$) as indicated in the significant value of .913. This result indicates that pupils' interpersonal skills did not affect pupils' school performance. Thus, null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between pupils' school performance and their social skills in terms of interpersonal skills" is accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils' school performance can be attributed to other factors other than their interpersonal skills. Lazar (2021) asserted that interpersonal skills known as soft social skills only facilitate behaviors and competence in interaction and it only help develop verbal communication and leadership development because it involves initiating personal interaction with others in school environment.

Further, results showed that pupils' interactive skills denote "Negligible correlation" to pupils' school performance ($r=.081$) as indicated in the significant value of .551. This results imply that pupils' interactive skills did not affect pupils' school performance. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between pupils' school performance and pupils' social skills in terms of interactive skills" is accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils' school performance is attributed to other factors other than their interactive skills.

This finding was supported by Lazar (2021) who revealed that pupils' learning performance which is reflective of the general school performance is predisposed by their cognitive development, readiness, and maturity. Additionally, it was emphasized that pupils' emotional development and readiness are factors that allow pupils to engage in learning.

Subsequently, pupils' personal skills denote "Negligible correlation" to pupils' school performance ($r=.026$) as indicated in the significant value of .850). This results imply that pupils' personal skills did not affect pupils' school performance. Henceforth, this present study indicated that the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between pupils' school performance and pupils' social skills in terms of personal skills" is accepted because pupils' school performance and personal skills were found to have negligible correlation. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils' school performance is attributed to other factors other than their personal skills.

This finding was supported by Baltazar (2021) who pointed out that pupils' learning and school performance are influenced more on their cognitive and mental readiness and maturity. Pupils' active learning is the influenced by their predictive and intellectual development, readiness, and the provocative learning environment. Personal skills, however, only help pupils successfully relate with others and for self-regulations.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The development of pupils' social skills in terms of interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills are believed to contribute to pupils' ability to relate and develop interpersonal, interactive, and personal relationships with other learners in the classroom environment which are contributory to their social-relationships which allow them to understand not only their individualities but will help them adjust and understand others.

Pupils' school performance is measured in terms of their academic and learning achievements which is usually described based on their grades. These school performance is influenced by pupils' cognitive or mental development, readiness, and maturity. Researches on interpersonal, interactive, and personal skills development negligibly correlated to pupils' academic and learning achievements or performance.

There are different approaches in developing pupils' social skills which are instrumental in the development of their social relationships in the school community. However, pupils' academic and learning success are attributed to their cognitive and mental development and maturity as well as proper academic trainings inside the classroom. Additionally, it should be emphasized that the learning environment and atmosphere set by teachers contribute pupils' learning interest which according to research will also inspire and motivate learning.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will be made aware of the social skills development and maturity among first graders and how these contribute or influence their cognitive and mental readiness in order to improve learning and academic performance so that DepEd Division officials will develop social-academic development-oriented framework which benefit public school learners.

School Principals/School Heads are recommended to provide support to teachers' instructional competence through an intensified training and seminar-workshops in order to help develop strategies in improving pupils' academic and learning performance to be at par with learners from private schools.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously develop and enhance their skills in developing and designing authentic learning materials which help pupils master the least mastered learning competencies in the different learning areas.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and ensure parent-teachers collaboration in the education of their children. They are also enjoined to provide an inclusive support to their children's education through the provision of learner-centered home school learning environment.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide the needed logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization of information and communication technology resources which help support pupils' learning and school performance.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct a similar investigation that thoroughly explore the correlation of social skills to pupils' learning achievements and other correlates that help inspire pupils to learn and improve their academic and learning achievements.

References

- Acevedo, E. (2021). Interpersonal Skills for academic preparedness of public school learners: Different Perspectives. *Journal of Learning Development*, 55 (8): 765-772.
- Anderson, J. R. (2020). From recurrent choice to skilled learning: A reinforcement learning model. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 135, 184–206.
- Ballard, D. H., Hayhoe, M. M., Pook, P. K., & Rao, R. P. N. (2021). Deictic codes for the embodiment of cognition. *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 20, 723–742.
- Baltazar, S. (2021). Peer Assisted Learning, Skills Development and Generation Y: A Case Study of a First-Graders Unite." *Journal of Education and Humanities* 27 (3): 210–24.
- Barrientos, A., (2021). Interactive Learning and pupils' academic development: A New Paradigm for teaching-learning. *Change* 27 (6): 12–25.
- Bernardino, A. (2020). "Relationship among soft skills, hard skills, and innovativeness of knowledge workers in the knowledge economy era." *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 52: 35-44.
- Chang, I. and Neza, L. (2021). Affective teaching: a method to enhance classroom management. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 27(3), 323-332.
- Ciappei, A. (2021). Developing cognitive-social-emotional competencies to enhance academic learning. *Psychology in the Schools*, 42(4), 405-417.
- Connelly, R (2021). Importance of social skills in the elementary grades. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 29(3), 409-419.
- Del Prette, H. (2021). Dealing with feelings: how children negotiate the worlds of emotions and social relationships. *Cognitive, Creier, Comportament/Cognition, Brain, Behavior*, 11(1).
- Del Puerto, L. (2020). Social Skills and Academic Performance among Grade 10 Students of the University of Bohol – University High School. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331090638>
- Doyle, H. (2020). Relations between teacher and classroom activity variables and the classroom behaviors of prekindergarten children in Chapter 1 funded programs. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 16, 253–282. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/U4pwu7>, (accessed last 16 April 2023).
- Fabria, E., & Romero, F. J. (2021). Body percussion: social competence between equals using the method BAPNE in Secondary Education
- Fu, W.-T., & Anderson, J. (2020). Solving the credit assignment problem: Explicit and implicit learning of action sequences with probabilistic outcomes. *Psychological Research*, 72, 321–330.
- Garcia, A and Benitez-Sellina (2020). Kindergarten predictors of boys' stable behavior problems at the end of elementary school. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 23(6), 751- 766. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/F25gb1>, (accessed last 19 April 2023).
- Gresham and Elliot M. (2020). Role of social performance in predicting learning problems: Prediction of risk using logistic regression analysis. 33(6).
- Grisi, L. (2020). The effect of social skills interventions in the primary school. *Educational Psychology in Practice*, 55(1), 33-51.

- Hay, D. (2020). Pro-social development. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 35, 29-71. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/g7E7tf>, (accessed last 7 April, 2023).
- Hekman, N. (2021). *On the self-regulation of behavior*. New York: Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/VAm7kQ>, (accessed last 24 April 2023).
- Isaac, K. (2021). Grading grown-ups 2002: how do American kids and adults relate? Key findings from a national study. ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED473459.
- Kapur, H. (2021). Some social determinants of self-monitoring reinforcement systems. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 5, 449-455. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/5ABZxJ>
- Katz, L. G., & McClellan, D. E. (2021). Fostering children's social competence: The teacher's role. National Association for the Education of Young Children.
- Keele, S., Ivry, R., Mayr, U., Hazeltine, E., & Heuer, H. (2020). The cognitive and neural architecture of sequence representation. *Psychological Review*, 110, 316-339.
- Lazar, Alexander (2021). Active Learning and Interpersonal Skills Development among First-Generation Students. *International Studies Perspectives*, pp. 1-22. California State University, USA.
- Martin, A. (2021). Using interactive learning to improve students' engagement. K to 12 resources for teachers. *Journal of Curriculum and Development*. Volume 1, No. 1, pp. 210-225
- Martinez, N. and McLeod, H. (2020). Competence, persistence, and success: The positive psychology of behavioral skill instruction. *Psychol. Schs.*, 41: 19-30. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/Kphjyd>, (accessed last 7 April 2023).
- Moira, Rukhsar, and Smrutihara Biswal (2020). "Soft skills in the status quo." *International Journal of Physical and Social Sciences* 2.5: 212-223.
- Paroginog, R. (2019). Social Skills and Academic Performance among Grade 10 Students of the University of Bohol – University High School. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331090638>
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2021). *Attitudes and persuasion: Classic and contemporary approaches*. Dubuque: Wm. C. Brown.
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2021). The elaboration likelihood model. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology & Aging*, 19, 123-205.
- Raja, H. (2020). "Teaching Soft Skills: A Necessity in Modern Era." *Research Journal of English Language and Literature (RJELAL)*. Vol.7(1).
- Raja, H. and Grisi, L. (2020). Improving social skills: A training presentation to parents. *Education*, 126(2), 251-258. Retrieved April 19, 2023, from Academic Search Premier database.
- Sales, R. (2021). Looking at classroom management through a social and emotional learning lens. *Theory into Practice*, 42(4), 313-318.
- Silva, C. (2021). "The Impact of Simulations on Higher-Level Learning." *Journal of Public Affairs Education* 18 (2): 397-422.
- Tan, C. (2021). "A study on soft skill development among pupils in the public school" *MOJEM: Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Management*, 3.2 (2017): 32-50.
- Ylagan, Ilana, and Aaron, Yadin (2021) "Soft skills an important key for employability in the" shift to a service-driven economy" era." *International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management, and e-Learning* 3.5: 416.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rostie C. Napone

Department of Education
Cagayan de Oro City – Philippines

Dr. Emmanuel Alex Bercero

St. Peter's College – Philippines